

Awareness of Human Microbiome May Promote Healthier Lifestyle and More Positive Environmental Attitudes

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Supplementary Information

S2: Supplementary Note: IHMCSA consortium member list

S3-S20: Supplementary figures and tables

S21-S26: The survey questionnaire (Supplementary Method)

Supplementary Note: International Human Microbiome Coordination and Support Action (IHMCSA) Consortium Members

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Suppl. Table 1
Demographics/Population characteristics

	France n=720		Germany n=705		South Korea n=714		Taiwan n=719	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
Gender								
Male	339	47%	344	49%	350	49%	350	49%
Female	379	53%	360	51%	363	51%	367	51%
Other	1	0%	1	0%	0	0%	0	0%
Prefer not to say	1	0%	0	0%	1	0%	2	0%
Age								
18-24 years old	51	7%	62	9%	95	14%	80	11%
25-34 years old	126	18%	109	15%	72	10%	98	14%
35-44 years old	108	15%	109	15%	99	14%	134	19%
45-54 years old	128	18%	113	16%	148	21%	131	18%
55-64 years old	124	17%	161	23%	215	30%	209	29%
65+ years old	183	25%	151	21%	85	12%	67	9%
Education								
Higher education degree	499	69%	570	81%	333	47%	377	52%
No higher education	221	31%	135	19%	381	53%	342	48%
Work in healthcare/life sciences								
No	642	89%	625	89%	663	93%	616	86%
Yes	78	11%	80	11%	51	7%	103	14%
Belief								
Believe in God	218	30%	218	31%	156	22%	129	18%
Believe in some sort of spirit or life force	202	28%	253	36%	309	43%	484	67%
Believe in none of both	300	42%	234	33%	249	35%	106	15%

Note. See Supplementary Material (Demographics part) for quota sources. Age quotas were spread in three groups: 18-34 years old, 35-54 years old and 55+ years old.

Suppl. Figure 1

Estimated network structure of attitudes to HM

Note: Nodes (the circles) represent attitudes regarding HM and are grouped per color. Orange: reported familiarity (1); Blue: estimated role for one's physical health (2) and mental well-being (3); Green: attitudes to monitoring one's microbiome health: willingness to monitor (4), HM health estimation relying on one's bodily experience (5) and information/techniques from healthcare professionals (6); Yellow: preferred ways of HM maintenance/improvement: via lifestyle adjustment (7) and buying special products (8). Thicker lines represent stronger connections. Total sample: $N=2,858$; France: $n=720$; Germany: $n=705$; South Korea: $n=714$; Taiwan: $n=719$.

Suppl. Figure 2

Centrality plot of attitudes to HM

Note: Total sample: $N=2,858$; France: $n=720$; Germany: $n=705$; South Korea: $n=714$; Taiwan: $n=719$.

Suppl. Figure 3
Edge stability plot

Note: Estimation of edge stability using non-parametric bootstrapping (1,000 replications) with edge weight ordered from highest to lowest. Bootstrapped confidence intervals are shown in grey (wider area indicates lower stability). The red line shows bootstrapped mean values for edge weights, while black dots show edge weight in the original network. The y-axis labels have been omitted to avoid cluttering. Total sample: $N=2,858$; France: $n=720$; Germany: $n=705$; South Korea: $n=714$; Taiwan: $n=719$.

Suppl. Figure 4

Stability of network structure using case-dropping subset bootstrapping

Note: Parametric bootstrap analysis showing the correlation between the centrality measures (strength, closeness, betweenness) of estimated (original) and the bootstrapped network (1,000 replications). The lines indicate mean correlations per index, while the colored areas show the range between the 2.5th and the 97.5th quantile). Total sample: $N=2,858$; France: $n=720$; Germany: $n=705$; South Korea: $n=714$; Taiwan: $n=719$.

Suppl. Figure 6
Edge stability plot per country

A. France

B. Germany

C. South Korea

D. Taiwan

Note: Estimation of edge stability using non-parametric bootstrapping (1,000 replications) with edge weight ordered from highest to lowest. Bootstrapped confidence intervals are shown in grey (wider area indicates lower stability). Red lines show bootstrapped mean values for edge weights, while black dots show edge weight in the original network. The y-axis labels have been omitted to avoid cluttering. Total sample: $N=2,858$; France: $n=720$; Germany: $n=705$; South Korea: $n=714$; Taiwan: $n=719$.

Suppl. Figure 7

Stability of network structure per country using case-dropping subset bootstrapping

Note: Parametric bootstrap analysis showing the correlation between the centrality measures (strength, closeness, betweenness) of estimated (original) and the bootstrapped network (1,000 replications). The lines indicate mean correlations per index, while the colored areas show the range between the 2.5th and the 97.5th quantile). Total sample: $N=2,858$; France: $n=720$; Germany: $n=705$; South Korea: $n=714$; Taiwan: $n=719$.

Suppl. Figure 8

Perceived familiarity with HM. Score distribution per country

Note: Respondents were asked (after a short information display on human microbiome and its role in health) how did they know about human microbiome. Total sample: $N=2,858$; France: $n=720$; Germany: $n=705$; South Korea: $n=714$; Taiwan: $n=719$.

Suppl. Figure 9

Perceived familiarity with HM. Contribution to score points per country

Note: Respondents were asked (after a short information display on human microbiome and its role in health) how much they knew about human microbiome. Total sample: $N=2,858$; France: $n=720$; Germany: $n=705$; South Korea: $n=714$; Taiwan: $n=719$.

Suppl. Figure 10

The estimated role of HM for one's physical health. Score distribution per country

Note: Respondents were asked how much they thought their microbiome affects their physical health. Total sample: $N=2,858$; France: $n=720$; Germany: $n=705$; South Korea: $n=714$; Taiwan: $n=719$.

Suppl. Figure 11

The estimated role of HM for one's physical health. Contribution to score points per country

Note: Respondents were asked how much they thought their microbiome affects their physical health. Total sample: $N=2,858$; France: $n=720$; Germany: $n=705$; South Korea: $n=714$; Taiwan: $n=719$.

Suppl. Figure 12

The estimated role of HM for one's mental wellbeing. Score distribution per country

Note: The respondents were asked how much they thought their microbiome affects their mental wellbeing. Total sample: $N=2,858$; France: $n=720$; Germany: $n=705$; South Korea: $n=714$; Taiwan: $n=719$.

Suppl. Figure 13

The estimated role of HM for one's mental wellbeing. Contribution to score points per country

Note: Respondents were asked how much they thought their microbiome affects their mental wellbeing. Total sample: $N=2,858$; France: $n=720$; Germany: $n=705$; South Korea: $n=714$; Taiwan: $n=719$.

Suppl. Figure 14

Willingness to monitor one's microbiome health. Score distribution per country

Note: The respondents were asked how willing they were to monitor their microbiome health. Total sample: $N=2,858$; France: $n=720$; Germany: $n=705$; South Korea: $n=714$; Taiwan: $n=719$.

Suppl. Figure 15

Willingness to monitor one's microbiome health. Contribution to score points per country

Note: Respondents were asked how willing they were to monitor their microbiome health. Total sample: $N=2,858$; France: $n=720$; Germany: $n=705$; South Korea: $n=714$; Taiwan: $n=719$.

Suppl. Figure 16

Relying on one's feelings and bodily experience in estimating one's microbiome health. Score distribution per country

Note: The respondents were asked to rate how much they agreed that they mainly rely on their feelings and bodily experience to estimate the health of their microbiome. Total sample: $N=2,858$; France: $n=720$; Germany: $n=705$; South Korea: $n=714$; Taiwan: $n=719$.

Suppl. Figure 17

Relying on one's feelings and bodily experience in estimating one's microbiome health. Contribution to score points per country

Note: Respondents were asked to rate how much they agreed that they mainly rely on the information and techniques from healthcare professionals to estimate the health of their microbiome. Total sample: $N=2,858$; France: $n=720$; Germany: $n=705$; South Korea: $n=714$; Taiwan: $n=719$.

Suppl. Figure 18

Relying on the information/techniques from healthcare professionals to estimate one's microbiome health. Score distribution per country

Note: The respondents were asked to rate how much they agreed that they mainly rely on the information and techniques from healthcare professionals to estimate the health of their microbiome. Total sample: $N=2,858$; France: $n=720$; Germany: $n=705$; South Korea: $n=714$; Taiwan: $n=719$.

Suppl. Figure 19

Relying on the information/techniques from healthcare professionals to estimate one's microbiome. Contribution to score points per country

Note: Respondents were asked to rate how much they agreed that they mainly rely on the information and techniques from healthcare professionals to estimate the health of their microbiome. Total sample: $N=2,858$; France: $n=720$; Germany: $n=705$; South Korea: $n=714$; Taiwan: $n=719$.

Suppl. Figure 20

Preference to improve/sustain one's microbiome health by adjusting one's lifestyle. Score distribution per country

Note: The respondents were asked to rate how much they agreed that they prefer the health of their microbiome to improve/sustain one's microbiome health by adjusting their lifestyle (such as diet and exercise). Total sample: $N=2,858$; France: $n=720$; Germany: $n=705$; South Korea: $n=714$; Taiwan: $n=719$.

Suppl. Figure 21

Preference to improve/sustain one's microbiome health by adjusting one's lifestyle. Contribution to score points per country

Note: Respondents were asked to rate how much they agreed that they prefer the health of their microbiome to improve/sustain one's microbiome health by adjusting their lifestyle such as diet and exercise. Total sample: $N=2,858$; France: $n=720$; Germany: $n=705$; South Korea: $n=714$; Taiwan: $n=719$.

Suppl. Figure 22

Willingness to buy special products to improve one's microbiome health. Score distribution per country

Note: Respondents were asked to rate how much they agreed that they were willing to buy special products to improve the health of their microbiome. Total sample: $N=2,858$; France: $n=720$; Germany: $n=705$; South Korea: $n=714$; Taiwan: $n=719$.

Suppl. Figure 23

Willingness to buy special products to improve one's microbiome health. Contribution to score points per country

Note: The respondents were asked to rate how much they agreed that they were willing to buy special products to improve the health of their microbiome. Total sample: $N=2,858$; France: $n=720$; Germany: $n=705$; South Korea: $n=714$; Taiwan: $n=719$.

Suppl. Figure 24

Willingness to participate in citizen science projects regarding HM. Score distribution per country

Note: Respondents were asked to rate how much they would be willing to participate in research projects where citizens collect and share data on their microbiome to promote public health. Total sample: $N=2,858$; France: $n=720$; Germany: $n=705$; South Korea: $n=714$; Taiwan: $n=719$.

Suppl. Figure 25

Willingness to participate in citizen science projects regarding HM. Contribution to score points per country

Note: Respondents were asked to rate how much they would be willing to participate in research projects where citizens collect and share data on their microbiome to promote public health. Total sample: $N=2,858$; France: $n=720$; Germany: $n=705$; South Korea: $n=714$; Taiwan: $n=719$.

Suppl. Figure 26

Mean ratings of perceptions of microorganisms before and after reflection on one's microbiome

Note: The scores on a 7-point Likert scale range from 1 for “extremely negative” to 7 for “extremely positive”. Total sample: $N=2,858$; France: $n=720$; Germany: $n=705$; South Korea: $n=714$; Taiwan: $n=719$.

Suppl. Figure 27

Change in self-image. Contribution to score points per county

Note: Respondents were asked whether the awareness about microbiome influenced the image of who they are. Total sample: $N=2,858$; France: $n=720$; Germany: $n=705$; South Korea: $n=714$; Taiwan: $n=719$.

Suppl. Figure 28

Attitude change towards microbes and the microbial world. Contribution to score points per country

Note: Respondents were asked how the awareness about microbiome makes them look at microbes and the microbial world. Total sample: $N=2,858$; France: $n=720$; Germany: $n=705$; South Korea: $n=714$; Taiwan: $n=719$.

Supplementary Method. Human microbiome survey questionnaire

A. Introduction.

Dear participant,

You are invited to take part in a research study.

We examine the attitudes people may hold about human microbiome.

This research study is being conducted by [name of the researcher]. If you have questions or comments about this study, you may contact the researcher [contact email of the researcher].

You must be at least 18 years old to take part in this study. By proceeding to the survey questions, you certify that you are 18 years old or older.

If you choose to participate, we will ask you to answer a few questions. The survey will take about 6 minutes to complete. There are no specific risks or benefits associated with participating.

Taking part in this study is voluntary. You may choose to not participate or end your participation at any time.

The information you share will be anonymized and will not be connected back to you. Results from this study may be published or presented at research conferences. The anonymous data may be shared with other researchers via an online data repository.

By clicking the “Next page” button to enter the survey, you agree to participate in this research study.

“Next page”

B. Demographics.

First, please answer a few general questions.

1.

Please select your gender:

- Male
- Female
- Other
- Prefer not to say

2.

How old are you?

- Less than 18 years old (**respondents choosing this category were automatically screened out*)
- 18-24 years old
- 25-34 years old
- 35-44 years old
- 45-54 years old
- 55-64 years old
- 65+ years old

3.

Have you obtained a higher education degree (professional or academic)?

- No
- Yes

4.

Do you work in healthcare or life sciences?

- No
- Yes

5.

Which of these statements comes closest to your beliefs? (**this question was optional to answer*)

- You believe there is a God.
- You believe that there is some sort of spirit or life force.
- You don't believe that there is any sort of spirit, God or life force.

C. Main part

1.

What images or words come to your mind first when you think about microbes?

2.

Do you think these first images/words are more positive or negative?

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Extremely negative			Neutral			Extremely positive

3.

The human microbiome is a community of living microorganisms that inhabit the parts of the human body, such as gut or skin. Recent scientific studies suggest that

the microbiome plays an important role in our physical health, especially in digestion and immune system. It also appears to affect one's mood and contribute to our mental well-being.

4.
How much do you know about the human microbiome?

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
No knowledge at all		Not sure			A lot of knowledge	

5.
What are your main sources of information on microbiome (select up to 3 items from the list):

- Internet websites/blogs
- Social media (e.g., Facebook, TikTok, Instagram)
- Television
- Press
- Healthcare professionals
- Friends and family
- Scientific journals
- Companies offering special products
- Other
- None of the above

6.
How much do you think your microbiome affects your physical health?

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Not at all		Not sure			Very much so	

7.
How much do you think your microbiome affects your mental well-being?

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Not at all		Not sure			Very much so	

8.
How willing are you to monitor the health of your microbiome?

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Not at all		Neutral			Extremely	

9.
How much do you agree with these statements:

To estimate the health of my microbiome I mainly rely on my own feelings and bodily experience.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Strongly disagree		Neutral			Strongly agree	

To estimate the health of my microbiome I mainly rely on the information and techniques from healthcare professionals.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Strongly disagree		Neutral			Strongly agree	

10.
How much do you agree with these statements:

I prefer to improve or sustain the health of my microbiome by adjusting my lifestyle (such as diet and exercise).

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Strongly disagree		Neutral			Strongly agree	

I am willing to buy special products to improve the health of my microbiome.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Strongly disagree		Neutral			Strongly agree	

11.
Please pause for a moment and think about this:
There are trillions of living microorganisms inside your body. Actually, more than the

number of cells your body is made of. These microorganisms form communities and contribute to your health and well-being.

12.
How does this thought make you feel? Please share your thoughts and feelings.

--

13.
Are your feelings and thoughts more positive or negative?

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Extremely negative			Neutral		Extremely positive	

14.
Does the awareness about microbiome influence the image of who you are?

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Not at all			Undecided		Very much so	

15.
How does awareness about the human microbiome make you look at microbes and the microbial world?

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
More negatively			No change		More positively	

16.
Would you like to share more thoughts on this?

--

17.
How willing would you be to participate in research projects where citizens collect and share data on their microbiome to promote public health?

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Not at all			Neutral		Extremely	

D. Debriefing

Thank you for your time and contribution to our study.

Please remember: the human microbiome is a relatively new field of research. Currently available information provides some insights but is not definitive. Microbiomes are very complex. Much research is still needed to test new treatments, devices and dietary supplements.

If you want to leave a comment, you can do it here: